

Table S1: Constructs generated in this study. Sequences are accessible at GB cloning website using the GB database ID.

Level 0 GBparts		
GB database ID	Name	Category
GB1438	AsCpf1	CDS
GB1439	LbCpf1	CDS
GB1442	AtU6-26::AsDR	Other
GB1443	AtU6-26::LbDR	Other
GB1444	HDV	Other
GB2478	AtUBQ10	PROM+5UTR

Level 1 GBparts		
GB database ID	Name	Category
GB1750	35s::AsCpf1::35s	TU
GB1751	35s::LbCpf1::35s	TU
GB1753	AtU6-26::AsDR:gXT1::HDV	TU
GB1754	AtU6-26::AsDR:gXT1::PolyA	TU
GB1755	AtU6-26::AsDR::gXT2 A::HDV	TU
GB1756	AtU6-26::AsDR::gXT2 B::HDV	TU
GB1757	AtU6-26::AsDR::gTFL1::HDV	TU
GB1758	AtU6-26::AsDR:gFT::HDV	TU
GB1759	AtU6-26::AsDR:gCBP::HDV	TU
GB1760	AtU6-26::AsDR::gScRub::HDV	TU
GB1761	AtU6-26::LbDR::gXT1::HDV	TU
GB1762	AtU6-26::LbDR::gXT1::PolyA	TU
GB1763	AtU6-26::LbDR::gXT2 A::HDV	TU
GB1764	AtU6-26::LbDR::gXT2 B::HDV	TU
GB1765	AtU6-26::LbDR::TFL1::HDV	TU
GB1766	AtU6-26::LbDR::gFT::HDV	TU
GB1767	AtU6-26::LbDR::CBP::HDV	TU

GB1768	AtU6-26::LbDR::ScRub::HDV	TU
GB1769	AtU6-26::gXT1::gXT2	TU
GB1770	AtU6-26::gXT2 A::psgRNA	TU
GB1771	AtU6-26::gXT2 B::psgRNA	TU
GB1772	AtU6-26::gTFL1::psgRNA	TU
GB1773	AtU6-26::gFT::psgRNA	TU
GB1774	AtU6-26::gCBP::psgRNA	TU
GB1775	AtU6-26::gScRub::psgRNA	TU
GB1776	AtU6-26::synTAADR::TFL1::HDV	TU
GB2050	AtU6-26::synTTADR::TFL1::HDV	TU
GB2051	AtU6-26::synTACDR::TFL1::HDV	TU
GB2052	AtU6-26::synTGTDR::TFL1::HDV	TU
GB2053	AtU6-26::synTAADR::FT::HDV	TU
GB2054	AtU6-26::synTACDR::FT::HDV	TU
GB2055	AtU6-26::synTGTDR::FT::HDV	TU
GB2056	AtU6-26::synTCADR::FT::HDV	TU
GB2479	AtUBQ10::LbCpf1::Tnos	TU
GB2480	AtU6-26::gPDS3-D1::HDV	TU
GB2481	AtU6-26::gPDS3-D2::HDV	TU
GB2482	At2S3::DsRED::T35S	TU
GB2483	DsRED(TU)_LbCpf1(TU)_guides	MODULE

Leve>1 GBparts		
GB database ID	Name	Category
GB1629	NptII-AsCpf1-XT1	Module
GB1630	NptII-LbCpf1-XT1	Module
GB1179	NptII-sgRNA_MYB12-hCas9	Module
GB1780	NptII-crRNA_MYB12-AsCpf1	Module
GB1781	NptII-crRNA_MYB12-LbCpf1	Module

Table S2: oligonucleotides used in this study.

Name	Sequence (5'-3')
crRNA TFL1 Cpf1 +	AGATACTGTGGGACTGAATGAATC
crRNA TFL1 Cpf1 -	GGCCGATTCATTCAGTCCCACAGT
crRNA TFL1 Cas9 +	ATTGTGACTGTCATTTTAACTGT
crRNA TFL1 Cas9 -	AAACACAGTTAAAATGACAGTCA
crRNA FT Cpf1 +	AGATCAAGATCTATTGGCCTAAGA
crRNA FT Cpf1 -	GGCCTCTTAGGCCAATAGATCTTG
crRNA FT Cas9 +	ATTGGCCAATAGATCTTGTAATA
crRNA FT Cas9 -	AAACTTTTACAAGATCTATTGGC
crRNA Cas9 XT2B +	ATTGCTCTGATTGCACAATGGAA
crRNA Cas9 XT2B -	AAACTTCCATTGTGCAATCAGAG
crRNA Cpf1 XT2B +	AGATGCTCTGATTGCACAATGGAA
crRNA Cpf1 XT2B -	GGCCTTCCATTGTGCAATCAGAGC
crRNA XT2A Cpf1 +	AGATTCCACTAGTTTTTTCCCAAT
crRNA XT2A Cpf1 -	GGCCATTGGGAAAAAACTAGTGGA
crRNA XT2A Cas9 +	ATTGAAAATTGGGAAAAAACTAG
crRNA XT2A Cas9 -	AAACCTAGTTTTTTCCCAATTTTC
crRNA Cpf1 Rubisco +	AGATGATGCAGATACTGGACCATG
crRNA Cpf1 Rubisco -	GGCCCATGGTCCAGTATCTGCATC
crRNA Cas9 Rubisco +	ATTGATGCAGATACTGGACCATG
crRNA Cas9 Rubisco -	AAACCATGGTCCAGTATCTGCAT
crRNA Cpf1 CBP +	AGATGAGGACAAACTACATCCAGG

crRNA Cpf1 CBP -	GGCCCCTGGATGTAGTTTGTCTC
crRNA Cas9 CBP +	ATTGAGGACAACTACATCCAGG
crRNA Cas9 CBP -	AAACCCTGGATGTAGTTTGTCTC
crRNA XT1 Cpf1 +	AGATTATGTAGGTGTATTTGGAAT
crRNA XT1 Cpf1 -	GGCCATTCCAAATACACCTACAT
crRNA XT1 Cas9 +	ATTGTGTAGGTGTATTTGGAATTC
crRNA XT1 Cas9 -	AAACGAATTCCAAATACACCTAC
synDR TFL1 F	ATTGTAATTTCTACTAAGTAGATACTGTGGGACTGAATGAATC
synDR TFL1 R	GGCCGATTCATTCAGTCCCACAGTATCTACTTAGTAGAAATTA
LbCpf1 XT1 multiplexing+	CTCGATTGTAATTTCTACTAAGTGTAGATTATGTAGGTGTATTTGGAATTAATTTCTAC
LbCpf1 XT1 multiplexing -	CTCAGTAGAAATTAATTCCAAATACACCTACATAATCTACACTTAGTAGAAATTACAAT
LbCpf1 XT2 multiplexing +	CTCGCTACTAAGTGTAGATTCCACTAGTTTTTTCCCAATTAATTTCTACTAAGTGTAGATTTTTTTTTTCGCT
LbCpf1 XT2 multiplezing -	CTCAAGCGAAAAAAAATCTACACTTAGTAGAAATTAATTGGGAAAAAACTAGTGGAAATCTACACTTAGT AG
Cpf1 XT1 polyA +	AGATTATGTAGGTGTATTTGGAATTTTTTTTT
Cpf1 XT1 polyA -	AGCGAAAAAAAATTCCAAATACACCTACATA
crRNA MYB12 Cas9 +	ATTGAAAGAGTTGTAGACTACGA
crRNA MYB12 Cas9 -	AAACTCGTAGTCTACAACCTCTTT
crRNA MYB12 Cpf1 +	AGATGAAGGATTATTGAGATGCGG
crRNA MYB12 Cpf1 -	AAACCCGCATCTCAATAATCCTTC
crRNA synDR_TTA TFL1 +	AAACCATGGTCCAGTATCTGCAT
crRNA synDR_TTA	GGCCGATTCATTCAGTCCCACAGTATCTACTAAGTAGAAATTA

TFL1 -	
crRNA synDR_TAC TFL1 +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTACGTAGATACTGTGGGACTGAATGAATC
crRNA synDR_TAC TFL1 -	GGCCGATTCATTCAGTCCCACAGTATCTACGTAGTAGAAATTA
crRNA synDR TGT TFL1 +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTGTGTAGATACTGTGGGACTGAATGAATC
crRNA synDR TGT TFL1 -	GGCCGATTCATTCAGTCCCACAGTATCTACACAGTAGAAATTA
crRNA synDR TAA FT +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTAAGTAGATCAAGATCTATTGGCCTAAGA
crRNA synDR TAA FT -	GGCCTCTTAGGCCAATAGATCTTGATCTACTTAGTAGAAATTA
crRNA synDR TAC FT +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTACGTAGATCAAGATCTATTGGCCTAAGA
crRNA synDR TAC FT -	GGCCTCTTAGGCCAATAGATCTTGATCTACGTAGTAGAAATTA
crRNA synDR TGT FT +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTGTGTAGATCAAGATCTATTGGCCTAAGA
crRNA synDR TGT FT -	GGCCTCTTAGGCCAATAGATCTTGATCTACACAGTAGAAATTA
crRNA synDR TCA FT +	ATTGTAATTTCTACTCAGTAGATCAAGATCTATTGGCCTAAGA
crRNA synDR TCA FT -	GGCCTCTTAGGCCAATAGATCTTGATCTACTGAGTAGAAATTA

PCR oligonucleotides	
ID	Sequence (5'-3')
NbXT1 F	ACCCTGATCACTCTCGTC
NbXT1 R	TTGTATTCTATATCTGCCAACATTC
TIDE seq XT1	CCACTCTTCAATCACTTCCC
NbXT2 F	GGCGATAACACCGTCTC
NbXT2 R	AGACATCAAAAAGTTATAGGAATAATC
TIDE seq XT2	GGTGACGGCGGATGGTTTAG
NbTFL1-3.1 F	GCTTACTGTGTCCTGTATAAAACTG
NbTFL1-3.1 R	GTAATCTCATATGTGGTATCGGAG
TFL1-3.1 seq	CAGCAACTATAAATGAGGCTC
NbTFL1-14.1 F/seq	GAGTAGATATTCCAAGACAGCAAC
NbTFL1-14.1 R	CACTGGAAAACCTCTGTAACAAC
NbFT F	CTAGAAAACCTATGGCTATAAGGG
NbFT R	GTTCTCGAGAGGTATAATATAGGC
FT seq	CACAAGCACGCATAGAAC
NbXT2B F	TGCACGGTTGTCCGAGTTTG
NbXT2B R	TTACTTGTGAATTGCTCTCTGGT
NbRubisco F	AGCGAAATTGAGTACCTCTTGAA
NbRubisco R	ACTCATATAGGCCACACAACAAT
NbCBP AB F	TGTCTAGACTGGTGCATTAATTC
NbCBP AB R	GTTGCCAAAAGGATCACTCAAAT
SIMYB12 F	GATGGACTGCAGAAGAAGATCAA
SIMYB12 R	AACATCGAAATTTGTACCTGAACT
AtPDS F1	CGAACCGACCCGAGAAGAGA

AtPDS R1	CTATTCAGGTGCGCGCTCA
AtPDS R2	GCCGACCATGGCTGGCAA

Table S3: indel frequency quantification based on the band densitometry analysis of the electrophoresis gels produced in these study (Figure S3b). No digested targets are omitted

Figure 1b: HDV vs PA							
Sample	Undigested Band	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel frequency	Mean	SEM
AsCpf1 HDV 1	999.326,0	7.851.246,0	4.666.882,0	0,07	3,77	5,73	1,32
AsCpf1 HDV 2	1.365.740,0	7.437.832,0	4.693.054,0	0,10	5,19		
AsCpf1 HDV 3	1.828.569,0	6.231.761,0	3.528.811,0	0,16	8,23		
LbCpf1 HDV 1	6.513.782,0	4.313.569,0	1.821.326,0	0,51	30,36	30,29	0,49
LbCpf1 HDV 2	7.588.681,0	4.596.569,0	2.259.104,0	0,53	31,11		
LbCpf1 HDV 3	6.455.610,0	3.787.154,0	2.622.104,0	0,50	29,42		
AsCpf1 PA 1	358.406,0	9.658.853,0	5.808.882,0	0,02	1,14	0,99	0,08
AsCpf1 PA 2	205.920,0	6.202.640,0	4.539.468,0	0,02	0,94		
AsCpf1 PA 3	218.920,0	6.995.125,0	5.304.004,0	0,02	0,88		
LbCpf1 PA 1	2.671.225,0	3.402.619,0	1.461.669,0	0,35	19,66	21,42	2,43
LbCpf1 PA 2	3.731.468,0	3.113.326,0	1.341.548,0	0,46	26,23		
LbCpf1 PA 3	3.788.296,0	5.094.104,0	2.464.104,0	0,33	18,38		

Figure 1c: Multiplexing							
Sample	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Promedio	SEM
LbCpf1 XT1 1	11.941.267	4.296.610	1.651.962	0,33	18,30	13,40	2,45
LbCpf1 XT1 2	13.909.480	2.681.832	1.053.841	0,21	11,21		
LbCpf1 XT1 3	13.015.581	2.330.175	974.770	0,20	10,70		
LbCpf1 XT2 1	11.321.995	3.860.146	980.305	0,30	16,30	14,72	3,33
LbCpf1 XT2 2	12.547.551	1.673.761	711.527	0,16	8,33		
LbCpf1 XT2 3	11.185.752	4.927.439	1.163.184	0,35	19,54		

Figure 2a: XT2A target						
Sample	Undigested	Digested	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Promedio	SEM
Cas9 XT2 1	9.114.116	1.160.376	0,1	5,82	5,47	0,64
Cas9 XT2 3	8.654.823	782.134	0,1	4,23		
Cas9 XT2 2	8.582.602	1.208.497	0,1	6,37		
AsCpf1 XT2 1	7.880.309	563.598	0,1	3,39	5,58	1,10
AsCpf1 XT2 2	7.288.409	1.055.619	0,1	6,54		
AsCpf1 XT2 3	6.517.853	987.497	0,1	6,81		
LbCpf1 XT2 1	5.408.782	1.151.205	0,2	9,20	6,52	1,34
LbCpf1 XT2 2	6.960.631	763.962	0,1	5,07		
LbCpf1 XT2 3	6.893.853	792.719	0,1	5,30		

Figure 2a: XT2B target							
Sample	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
Cas9 XT2B 1	15.154.108	1.137.569	540.426	0,10	5,12	15,92	6,80
Cas9 XT2B 2	8.954.459	3.398.962	2.954.719	0,42	23,52		
Cas9 XT2B 3	8.635.974	2.549.054	2.022.569	0,35	19,14		

Figure 2a: target TFL1 14.1.							
Muestra	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
TFL1 14.1 As 1	8470045,00	2066104,00	1472447,00	0,24	13,05	11,13	1,30
TFL1 14.1 As 2	8992238,00	1580619,00	1002305,00	0,18	9,21		
TFL1 14.1 As 3	7531681,00	1857225,00	1566205,00	0,25	13,20		
TFL1 14.1 Lb 1	6591539,00	4357711,00	2835468,00	0,66	41,79	35,62	4,41
TFL1 14.1 Lb 2	6776489,00	3403933,00	2659589,00	0,50	29,45		
TFL1 14.1 Lb 3	7431782,00	5053539,00	3197125,00	0,68	43,43		

Figure 2a: TFL1 3.1 target						
Sample	Undigested	Digested	Fraction cleaved	%Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
TFL1 3.1 Cas9 1	7.833.974,00	423.678,00	0,05	2,60	2,35	0,86
TFL1 3.1 Cas9 2	8.900.974,00	135.364,00	0,01	0,75		
TFL1 3.1 Cas9 3	6.810.782,00	534.920,00	0,07	3,71		
TFL1 3.1 As 1	4.723.175,00	872.062,00	0,16	8,12	9,22	0,60
TFL1 3.1 As 2	6.515.368,00	1.412.255,00	0,18	9,34		
TFL1 3.1 As 3	6.656.439,00	1.595.962,00	0,19	10,19		
TFL1 3.1 Lb 1	5.129.196,00	4.111.296,00	0,44	25,50	27,98	2,27
TFL1 3.1 Lb 2	6.411.489,00	5.272.075,00	0,45	25,92		
TFL1 3.1 Lb 3	4.795.347,00	5.735.196,00	0,54	32,52		

Figure 2a: target XT1.							
Sample	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel freq	Mean	SEM
Lb XT1 1	12.695.279	1.206.497	392.506	0,11	5,76	20,32	8,98
Lb XT1 2	6.776.196	6.972.640	3.168.347	0,60	36,71		
Lb XT1 3	9.087.217	3.317.104	1.275.841	0,34	18,50		

Figure 2a: target CBP									
Sample	Undigested	Unespecific 1	Unespecific 2	Specific 1	Specific 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
CBP Cas9 1	12.338.238	802.062	401.335	788.841	679.991	0,10	5,02	5,92	3,36
CBP Cas9 2	9.259.924	733.184	314.213	126.506	0	0,01	0,61		
CBP Cas9 3	10.815.823	675.770	401.305	2.377.841	1.133.962	0,23	12,13		
CBP Lb 1	12.381.116	559.648	381.577	2.134.154	810.062	0,18	9,50	6,77	2,65
CBP Lb 2	12.381.116	1.014.134	213.971	409.355	0	0,03	1,47		
CBP Lb 3	12.381.116	945.205	420.062	2.372.154	602.456	0,18	9,33		

Figure 2a: target FT.									
Sample	Undigested	Unspecific 1	Specific 1	Specific 2	Unspecific 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
Cas9 FT 1	11.048.610	2.063.225	2.607.953	0	820.577	0,17	8,67	9,76	0,78
Cas9 FT 2	8.219.903	1.628.690	2.659.832	0	623.749	0,21	11,27		
Cas9 FT 3	10.972.974	1.897.640	2.789.125	0	690.234	0,18	9,34		
LbCpf1 FT 1	6.007.518	691.113	2.780.912	1.645.326	457.749	0,40	22,40	25,24	3,49
LbCpf1 FT 2	4.982.640	419.506	2.061.790	1.218.790	0	0,38	21,12		
LbCpf1 FT 3	4.812.518	756.820	3.875.347	2.664.518	305.506	0,54	32,18		

Figure 2a: target RUBISCO.								
Sample	Undigested	Unspecific 1	Specific	Unspecific 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel frequency	Mean	SEM
Cas9 RUB 1	20.794.785	565.820	1.158.841	1.068.397	0,049	2,487	1,813	0,341
Cas9 RUB 2	20.423.886	171.385	676.113	534.062	0,031	1,563		
Cas9 RUB 3	19.546.563	804.184	616.234	1.390.811	0,028	1,388		
LbCpf1 RUB 1	16.469.472	0	3.422.104	0	0,172	9,008	10,124	0,562
LbCpf1 RUB 2	11.997.229	529.012	3.419.569	1.125.347	0,200	10,575		
LbCpf1 RUB 3	13.553.472	524.698	3.835.447	873.497	0,204	10,790		

Figure 3c: assessment of synDRs for TFL1 3.1 with AsCpf1.

Sample	Undigested	Digested	Fraction cleaved	%Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
As AsDR 1	8.103.681,00	530.506,00	0,06	3,12	7,88	2,41
As AsDR 2	4.852.004,00	1.258.426,00	0,21	10,89		
As AsDR 3	9.184.510,00	2.063.497,00	0,18	9,64		
As LbDR 1	8.266.510,00	2.149.205,00	0,21	10,91	10,79	0,32
As LbDR 2	9.249.681,00	2.217.912,00	0,19	10,19		
As LbDR 3	8.128.388,00	2.198.790,00	0,21	11,28		
As synTAA 1	4.450.660,00	1.259.305,00	0,22	11,71	10,76	2,34
As synTAA 2	4.792.489,00	669.284,00	0,12	6,33		
As synTAA 3	5.525.075,00	1.988.912,00	0,26	14,25		
As synTTA 1	7.015.439,00	1.893.447,00	0,21	11,26	12,99	1,11
As synTTA 2	7.346.731,00	2.286.205,00	0,24	12,67		
As synTTA 3	7.294.368,00	2.813.225,00	0,28	15,05		
As synTCA 1	8.850.439,00	1.830.962,00	0,17	8,97	11,74	1,92
As synTCA 2	5.831.903,00	1.501.962,00	0,20	10,83		
As synTCA 3	5.185.004,00	2.063.033,00	0,28	15,42		
As synTGT 1	4.012.761,00	2.917.296,00	0,42	23,91	20,83	1,60
As synTGT 2	6.733.418,00	3.418.761,00	0,34	18,56		
As synTGT 3	6.619.832,00	3.728.518,00	0,36	20,02		

Figure 3c: assessment of synDRs for TFL1 14.1 with AsCpf1.

Muestra	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
As AsDR 1	9.655.016,00	2.357.983,00	1.644.104,00	0,29	15,92	16,37	0,58
As AsDR 2	10.108.309,00	2.195.861,00	1.906.640,00	0,29	15,66		
As AsDR 3	9.855.087,00	2.671.589,00	1.963.468,00	0,32	17,53		
As LbDR 1	8.950.016,00	2.212.205,00	1.373.326,00	0,29	15,50	16,46	0,49
As LbDR 2	8.706.995,00	2.196.983,00	1.667.640,00	0,31	16,78		
As LbDR 3	9.284.995,00	2.532.690,00	1.690.033,00	0,31	17,09		
As synTAA 1	4.751.225,00	686.598,00	653.941,00	0,22	11,69	12,97	3,05
As synTAA 2	5.024.518,00	528.406,00	441.406,00	0,16	8,45		
As synTAA 3	2.963.569,00	863.941,00	663.355,00	0,34	18,77		
As synTTA 1	4.981.811,00	843.012,00	851.770,00	0,25	13,62	12,04	1,99
As synTTA 2	5.683.761,00	1.205.376,00	870.184,00	0,27	14,41		
As synTTA 3	9.484.560,00	968.477,00	772.577,00	0,16	8,08		
As synTCA 1	8.958.832,00	1.236.912,00	792.012,00	0,18	9,70	11,48	1,25
As synTCA 2	7.845.711,00	1.263.841,00	762.355,00	0,21	10,85		
As synTCA 3	6.746.468,00	1.421.669,00	930.012,00	0,26	13,89		
As synTGT 1	7.447.539,00	2.394.447,00	1.416.912,00	0,34	18,67	19,07	0,64
As synTGT 2	5.731.347,00	1.823.497,00	1.014.184,00	0,33	18,22		
As synTGT 3	6.020.397,00	1.897.669,00	1.565.033,00	0,37	20,32		

Figure 3c: assesment of synDRs for TFL1 3.1 with LbCpf1.

Sample	Undigested	Digested	Fraction cleaved	%Indel Frequency	Media	SEM
Lb AsDR 1	9.485.551,00	4.564.225,00	0,32	17,83	17,64	0,89
Lb AsDR 2	6.932.116,00	3.656.225,00	0,35	19,09		
Lb AsDR 3	8.117.409,00	3.389.912,00	0,29	16,01		
Lb LbDR 1	6.822.095,00	5.292.024,00	0,44	24,96	22,26	1,81
Lb LbDR 2	8.064.530,00	5.542.095,00	0,41	23,01		
Lb LbDR 3	9.996.966,00	5.174.196,00	0,34	18,82		
Lb synTAA 1	10.882.794,00	461.113,00	0,04	2,05	1,95	0,47
Lb synTAA 2	12.963.472,00	290.406,00	0,02	1,10		
Lb synTAA 3	12.658.794,00	714.548,00	0,05	2,71		
Lb synTTA 1	12.566.007,00	296.698,00	0,02	1,16	2,42	0,64
Lb synTTA 2	9.103.116,00	625.355,00	0,06	3,27		
Lb synTTA 3	12.083.401,00	713.648,00	0,06	2,83		
Lb synTCA 1	11.276.844,00	825.719,00	0,07	3,47	5,07	1,48
Lb synTCA 2	11.492.057,00	2.092.033,00	0,15	8,02		
Lb synTCA 3	11.270.380,00	888.719,00	0,07	3,72		
Lb synTGT 1	10.845.602,00	635.941,00	0,06	2,81	3,30	0,27
Lb synTGT 2	10.898.066,00	860.941,00	0,07	3,73		
Lb synTGT 3	9.673.823,00	685.941,00	0,07	3,37		

Figure 3c: assessment of synDRs for TFL1 14.1 with LbCpf1.

Muestra	Undigested	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	% Indel Frequency	Mean	SEM
As AsDR 1	10.276.744,00	6.023.267,00	5.667.622,00	0,53	31,60	30,41	0,75
As AsDR 2	9.810.401,00	5.348.338,00	4.312.995,00	0,50	29,02		
As AsDR 3	8.932.693,00	5.036.439,00	4.587.995,00	0,52	30,62		
As LbDR 1	8.161.894,00	5.406.024,00	5.144.359,00	0,56	33,96	32,18	1,69
As LbDR 2	9.156.016,00	4.643.439,00	4.267.116,00	0,49	28,81		
As LbDR 3	8.709.681,00	6.365.731,00	4.784.874,00	0,56	33,78		
As synTAA 1	9.490.945,00	481.719,00	535.962,00	0,10	4,97	4,77	0,23
As synTAA 2	9.651.865,00	624.083,00	267.577,00	0,08	4,32		
As synTAA 3	11.552.530,00	683.548,00	573.790,00	0,10	5,03		
As synTTA 1	10.582.501,00	528.376,00	215.213,00	0,07	3,34	5,23	1,08
As synTTA 2	10.958.966,00	809.104,00	922.276,00	0,14	7,07		
As synTTA 3	10.554.338,00	691.861,00	519.548,00	0,10	5,29		
As synTCA 1	9.453.803,00	1.446.447,00	1.262.811,00	0,22	11,84	11,02	0,98
As synTCA 2	10.910.945,00	1.774.468,00	1.450.711,00	0,23	12,15		
As synTCA 3	11.172.167,00	1.226.276,00	1.116.104,00	0,17	9,08		
As synTGT 1	11.539.238,00	812.598,00	601.497,00	0,11	5,62	7,62	1,61
As synTGT 2	10.451.723,00	1.314.861,00	1.372.640,00	0,20	10,81		
As synTGT 3	12.035.066,00	903.012,00	810.983,00	0,12	6,44		

Figure 3c: assesment of synDRs for FT with LbCpf1.

Sample	Undigested	Unespecific	Digested 1	Digested 2	Fraction cleaved	%Indel Frequency	Media	SEM
As AsDR 1	7.791.731,00	379.506,00	3.922.468,00	2.647.468,00	0,45	25,55	20,42	2,83
As AsDR 2	7.962.610,00	621.234,00	2.032.397,00	1.489.447,00	0,29	15,79		
As AsDR 3	9.133.167,00	755.113,00	3.399.347,00	2.126.104,00	0,36	19,90		
As LbDR 1	9.674.388,00	356.335,00	3.775.468,00	2.603.246,00	0,39	21,82	21,43	1,40
As LbDR 2	9.620.409,00	821.012,00	3.330.640,00	2.079.054,00	0,34	18,84		
As LbDR 3	9.769.045,00	685.698,00	4.411.175,00	3.061.317,00	0,42	23,63		
As synTAA 1	11.310.924,00	445.598,00	736.941,00	519.113,00	0,10	4,95	6,68	1,00
As synTAA 2	9.336.439,00	761.376,00	1.120.669,00	823.184,00	0,16	8,43		
As synTAA 3	10.428.338,00	852.740,00	1.036.062,00	629.113,00	0,13	6,65		
As synTAC 1	8.561.539,00	950.790,00	1.923.790,00	1.536.983,00	0,27	14,37	14,28	1,68
As synTAC 2	8.779.782,00	875.184,00	2.674.447,00	1.736.497,00	0,31	17,15		
As synTAC 3	11.602.187,00	1.270.447,00	2.063.861,00	1.435.205,00	0,21	11,33		
As synTGT 1	10.532.217,00	496.841,00	1.390.497,00	935.841,00	0,17	9,13	7,34	0,90
As synTGT 2	10.136.338,00	608.426,00	745.355,00	736.305,00	0,12	6,25		
As synTGT 3	8.475.439,00	1.639.640,00	847.941,00	643.012,00	0,13	6,64		

Table S4: stability of the different crRNAs of *TFL1* and *FT* loci. The stability has been measured as the $-\Delta G$ predicted by the Vienna RNA and Mfold software tools. For each loci, the sequence among the synthetic crRNAs are identical, only varying two nucleotides of the direct repeat loops (5'-UNN-3') which generates a different structure with different stability.

$-\Delta G$ TFL1 crRNAs		
5'-UNN-3'	Vienna RNA	Mfold
UAA	4	4.7; 4.1; 4
UUA	4	4.7; 4.3; 4.1; 4; 3.9
UAC	3.7	4.7; 4.6; 4.1; 4
UGU	5.6	6

$-\Delta G$ FT crRNAs		
5'-UNN-3'	Vienna RNA	Mfold
UAA	4.1	4.9; 4.9; 4.7; 4
UAC	3.9	4.9; 4.7; 4.5; 4.3; 4
UGU	3.3	4.9; 4.7; 4.3; 4
UCA	7.3	7; 6.5

$-\Delta G$ TFL1 WT crRNAs		
	Vienna RNA	Mfold
AsDR	5.5	4.1; 4.4; 4.5; 4.9
LbDR	5.8	4.9; 5; 5.4

$-\Delta G$ FT WT crRNAs		
	Vienna RNA	Mfold
AsDR	6.15	4.3; 4.4; 4.9; 5.1
LbDR	5.9	4.9; 5.6

Table S5: mapping stats and filtering parameters used in the WGS off-target analysis.

a) Read and mapping stats against the reference genome TAIR10.

Samples	Raw Reads	Clean Reads	% Remaining Reads	Properly Mapped reads	% Clean reads mapped
POOL	218876308	189905488	86,76 %	142472371	75,02 %
PDS-1-111	53615620	45729312	85,29 %	33841836	74,00 %
PDS-1-113	48045816	41316210	85,99 %	30879446	74,74 %
PDS-1-114	49526888	42845404	86,51 %	32132445	75,00 %
PDS-1-115	49177422	42282212	85,98 %	31058272	73,45 %
PDS-3-117	55059068	46790330	84,98 %	35722381	76,35 %
PDS-3-118	78323478	68581142	87,56 %	52700597	76,84 %
PDS-3-119	41661252	35192082	84,47 %	26186410	74,41 %
PDS-3-123	59969898	51610012	86,06 %	38797014	75,17 %
WT-104	38125478	32252932	84,60 %	23280192	72,18 %
WT-106	55280774	47793828	86,46 %	36127369	75,59 %

b) Parameters used in GATK, FREEBAYES, VARSCAN2, PINDEL and DELLY programs.

	PARAMETERS
GATK	QD < 2.0, FS > 60.0 MQ < 40.0, MQRankSum < -12.5, ReadPosRankSum < -8.0
FREEBAYES	-n 2, -m 20, -C 2, -F 0.2
VARSCAN2	By default
PINDEL	By default
DELLY	-p -a 0.04 -r 1 -f germline